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THE ROLE OF TESTING, ASSESSMENT AND EVALUATION IN TEACHING FOREIGN LANGUAGES IN THE REPUBLIC OF UZBEKISTAN

Laylohon Tolibjonovna Akhmedova

Doctor of Science in Pedagogy, Professor
Uzbekistan State World Languages University

Laylo011057@gmail.com

***Abstract.** The article is devoted to the role of testing, assessment and evaluation in teaching foreign languages in the Republic of Uzbekistan.*

The importance and relevance of studying foreign languages in the Republic of Uzbekistan, outlined in the Presidential Decree, is emphasized.

The scientific and methodological literature of scientists from near and far abroad and Uzbekistan is analyzed on the problem of conducting testing, assessment and evaluation in teaching foreign languages.

A comparative analysis of testing, assessment and evaluation in teaching foreign languages is carried out for methodological purposes. As a result of a comparative analysis of testing, assessment and evaluation in teaching foreign languages, the common features and differences between the designated methodological categories are identified and described.

***Key words:** testing, assessment, evaluation, foreign language, teaching, continuous education, technique, knowledge, skill, ability.*

INTRODUCTION

The integration of our state into the international community, the development of science and technology require that the younger generation have a good command of several foreign languages in order to function competitively in a multicultural world. Knowledge of a foreign language is one of the components of the professional competence of specialists of any profile.

Resolution of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. PP-5117 dated May 19, 2021 “On measures to raise activities to popularize the study of foreign languages in the Republic of Uzbekistan to a qualitatively new level” [1] once again confirms the importance of modernization and renewal in raising an educated and intellectually developed generation, which is the most important value and decisive force in the development of a democratic society.

The resolution is aimed at creating the necessary conditions for popularizing the study of foreign languages among the population and mastering them to perfection, integration of the implementation of internationally recognized programs and textbooks for teaching foreign languages at all stages of education, as well as the development of modern teaching skills among teachers; to coordinate the development of language learning methods and recommendations suitable for all categories of the population in order to introduce a chain of continuous education into the field of teaching foreign languages.

One of such methods in mastering foreign languages is testing, assessment and evaluation, which are a means of diagnosing the difficulties of language and speech material, a measure of effectiveness and a way to predict the success of teaching foreign languages.

This implies the relevance and importance of using testing, assessment and evaluation in teaching foreign languages in the Republic of Uzbekistan.

MAIN PART

The issues of testing, assessment and evaluation have attracted and are attracting the attention of both foreign and domestic researchers, in whose works one can become familiar with the basic principles of the theory of the testing process, assessment and evaluation.

These are scientists like Au, W., Black, P., & Wiliam, D., Gikandi, J. W., Morrow, D., & Davis, D., Kuncel, N. R., & Hezlett, S. A., Rogova G.V., Shchukin A.N., Muratkasimova K.Sh., Samatova B.R. etc.

All of these scientists consider testing, assessment and evaluation an effective research method that makes it possible to determine the degree of mastery of a certain set of knowledge, skills and abilities of students.

To reveal the role of tests, assessment and evaluation in teaching foreign languages, we will consider them separately and in comparison, with each other.

Test according to the definition of Shchukin A.N is (from the English test - testing, research) a system of tasks, the completion of which allows you to characterize the level of language proficiency using a special scale of results. Tests are also widely used to determine abilities, mental development and other personality characteristics"[12].

G.V. Rogova believes that testing is the most economical form of control [11]. We agree with the scientist's opinion, since the minimum time is given to complete the testing and, based on their results, the level of development of the student's knowledge, skills and abilities in a certain field of knowledge is determined.

Educational testing is one of the key components of today's language classrooms.

Testing is the most widely spread technique used for assessing students in the classroom. There are different tests: multiple choice, matching, true-false, fill-in-the-blanks tests, cloze and dictation procedures; assay exams; oral interview – but also tests differing in scope and structure from these well-known options. Technological

development has led to a number of new languages testing formats, including computer-based and computer-adaptive tests, audiotape-based oral proficiency interviews, and web-based testing [6].

A communicative test approximates to real language use in the real world. For example, dictation and cloze tests are considered non-communicative types, while role-play, letter and essay writing, following instruction, problem-solving, oral interview are communicative tests. But, for example, cloze tests provide a good way of gauging a student's written, reading, grammar and vocabulary proficiencies. Multiple choice tests and written assignments are good ways of assessing vocabulary, reading comprehension and writing skills [8].

Thus, language tests are simply instruments or procedures for gathering particular kinds of information, typically information having to do with students' language abilities. Tests have a variety of formats, length, item types, scoring criteria, and media.

Testing and assessment are often used interchangeably, assessment is an umbrella term for all types of measures used to evaluate student progress. Tests are a subcategory of assessment [10].

A test is a formal, systematic (usually paper-and-pencil) procedure used to gather information about students' achievement. Testing is the process of measuring a student's knowledge. This often involves administering standardized tests with predetermined questions. The purpose of testing is typically to gather data about an individual's proficiency or achievement level in a particular area. Testing can be used for diagnostic purposes like to identify strengths and weaknesses, for selection to make decisions about placements or admissions, or for certification to determine whether someone meets specific criteria. So, testing focuses on measuring specific knowledge, usually grammar tests. Assessment is a broader process that involves collecting information through various methods. Evaluation involves making decisions based on assessment [7].

The term assessment usually aligns with an end-of-course paper-and-pencil test designed to tell both teachers and students how much material the student doesn't know or hasn't yet mastered. "Assessment" is a very broad term that can cover formal exams and tests, both external and internal, which are structured and built into the fabric of the academic year, as well as more informal types of assessment that teachers undertake as a part of their day-to-day practice [3].

Assessment is a part of the lesson during which the teacher evaluates how students have mastered the material and use it in reception and production of texts in the oral and written forms. For example, we may use an oral interview to gather information about students speaking abilities, then give comments based on that information, and make a decision what material and activities we should use if the students need more work on oral fluency. Thus, within the foreign language classroom we reveal sources and zones of learning difficulties, see the effectiveness of materials and activities, encourage students' involvement in the learning process, track learners' upgrading their foreign language, and provide students with feedback about their foreign language learning progress for further classroom-based applications of language tests.

There are several types of assessment. Assessment may be formative or summative, it may be direct or indirect, also it may be formal and informal. Formal assessments are standardized tests that follow specific guidelines, procedures, and scoring criteria. They are typically administered under controlled conditions. The purpose of formal assessments is often used for making high-stakes decisions, such as placement. They are designed to be reliable, valid, and fair. Examples for formal assessment may be different standardized tests samples, such as SAT (SAT - Scholastic Aptitude Test / Scholastic Assessment Test — a standardized test for admission to US universities, as well as some universities in Singapore, Turkey, Hong Kong and Japan. It assesses the applicant's knowledge of English and mathematics, as well as his readiness to study at the university), ACT (ACT - American College Testing is a standardized test for admission to US colleges and

universities, as well as for transfer from one to another) and other types of standardized tests [5].

Compared to formal assessment informal assessment is a flexible and spontaneous. They are typically conducted in natural settings and provide qualitative insights. The purpose of Informal assessment is used for diagnostic purposes, to inform instruction, or to monitor progress over time.

For examples: Teachers or supervisors watching students or employees during activities to assess behaviors, skills, or understanding.

- Conversations/Interviews: Informal discussions with students or employees to gauge comprehension, problem-solving skills, or attitudes.
- Checklists: Quick, informal lists used to track skills or behaviors exhibited by individuals.
- Peer or Self-Assessment: Students or individuals assessing their own or peers' work based on criteria provided.

Formal assessment can include tests, quizzes, surveys, and questionnaires. Oral presentations, observation, exit surveys are examples of informal assessment. In some sense, formal and informal assessments can use the same methods [13].

To compare these both assessment types we may conclude that formal assessments have fixed structures, guidelines, and scoring methods, whereas informal assessments are more flexible and adaptable. Formal assessments are usually administered under the control while informal assessments can occur spontaneously and in various situations. Formal assessments results based on quantitative data like scores and rankings, while informal assessments provide qualitative insights based on observations and interviews [2].

Thus, both formal and informal assessments play important roles in assessing students' knowledge, skills, and abilities. The choice between them depends on the specific aim, content, and desired outcomes of the assessment process. We should identify learning goals and objectives with students' achievements and assessment. We need to create tools of assessment that will help us evaluate and understand

whether our learning outcomes have been achieved. But we also recognize that the assessment contributes to achieving some of our communicative goals. The tools of assessment we set up can be very different both in the skills they focus on, and also in the way they are executed.

The term “control” is often replaced by “assessment”. In general, assessment is collecting data for revealing the level of language proficiency achieved within a certain time period. In language assessment, we gather information in a systematic way with the help of language testing tools. The objects of the assessment are: a) knowledge and sub-skills (language competence); b) using knowledge and language sub-skills in the process of production and reception of speech and interaction (communicative competence); c) country-study and linguo-cultural knowledge of verbal and non-verbal behavior (socio cultural competence).

However, assessment is much more than tests. In language classroom it is important to clarify for both teachers and students, the terms as assessment, evaluation and testing and explain how they differ from one another. As, objective, content and final measurement should be aligned.

The term evaluation is all-inclusive and is the widest basis for collecting information in education. According to Brindley [4] evaluation is «conceptualized as broader in scope, and concerned with the overall program”. Evaluation involves looking at all factors that influence the learning process, i.e., syllabus objectives, course design, and materials.

In Uzbekistan evaluation in the system of continuing education is organized in the frame of five-score (1, 2, 3, 4, 5) marking. Assessment conducts within: 1) current control, 2) terminal (intermediate, or interval) control, 3) final control. But it is necessary to indicate here also preliminary control, because its role is important for organizing the ELT process. The process of assessing students’ performance is done by using variety of ways, techniques and forms. There are many techniques or activities of language performance in foreign language teaching. Dictation exercises, strip stories, tests and written assignments are all examples of different types of

techniques and activities suitable for foreign language learners. Simple dictation exercises require students to write down a passage read aloud by the teacher. These exercises offer an assessment of students' listening and writing skills. Strip stories require students to organize a short passage into the proper order after it has been taken apart and reorganized. Strip stories test reading comprehension and narrative awareness.

Evaluation involves looking at all factors that influence the learning process, i.e., syllabus objectives, course design, and materials [9].

Compared to Evaluation Assessment includes a broad range of activities and tasks that teachers use to evaluate student progress daily. Assessment is part of evaluation because it is concerned with the student and with what the student does. Assessment refers to a variety of ways of collecting information on a learner's language ability or achievement. It may include various methods beyond testing, such as observation, interviews, portfolios, or performance tasks. The primary goal of assessment is to gather comprehensive information about an individual, group, process, or system. It can be formative ongoing to monitor progress and inform instruction or summative. Assessment may be implemented in different purposes: diagnosing student needs, planning instruction, and many others. It can be formative, or summative.

CONCLUSION

So, at the end we can conclude, testing - a specific technique for gathering information about students' knowledge, skills, competence; assessment - involving various ways of collecting data including the use of tests; evaluation - making decisions based on the obtained evidence regarding the whole educational setting.

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